
A Study on Export of India's Manufactured Goods

Dr. Kajal Vijay Khandagale¹ & Dr. Ashish Stephan Kshirsagar²

¹Assistant Professor, Dept. of Agricultural Marketing,

College of Agriculture Business Management, Loni Tal-Rahata Dist: Ahmednagar

²I/C Principal, College of Agriculture Business Management, Loni Dist: Ahmednagar

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15130770

Abstract:

Manufactured goods export is one of the significant parts of the Indian economy. India is known as agriculture country but recent years in the composition basket increasing the share of manufactured goods in export due to modernization and diversification of the economy. The main objectives of this paper are to examine the total export of manufactured goods share in total export and analyze the total export of manufactured goods in pre and post reforms periods, to fulfill this objective researcher have used secondary data pre and post reform era. In this paper used different statistical techniques such mean, CAGR and independent t test for outcomes of the result. In pre reforms period Chemicals & related products and Handicrafts very inconsistency growth but in post reforms engineering goods and other Manu. Goods shows inconsistency growth its repressing in tables. The overall research paper has concluded that the manufactured goods export is important to contributing in the total export of India as well as there is significant growth in the post reform era as compare to the pre reform era. Manufactured goods export had been implementing the place of pride in the export basket of India and helpful to push up the Indian economy.

Keywords: *Composition, Manufactured Goods, Export, Foreign Trade, Reform Era*

Introduction:

Over the reform period observed that number of shifts have been taken place in the various aspects of India's foreign trade particularly in the terms of composition of commodities basket. The exports cover a wide range of traditional and non-traditional products while imports mainly consist of capital goods, petroleum products, raw materials, intermediates and chemicals to meet the ever-increasing industrial demands. (Bhat,2011,p-2) The diversification of the economy due to the reform process of industrialization and modernization has induced a number of changes in the composition of commodities baskets. The exports cover a wide range of traditional and non-traditional products while imports mainly consist of capital goods, petroleum products, raw materials, intermediates and

chemicals to meet the ever-increasing industrial demands. The composition India's foreign trade has undergone substantial changes. Composition of exports means goods that we are selling to other countries. At the time of Independence; our exports consisted mainly of agricultural products like Tea, Spices, tobacco and other raw materials etc. We were also exporting cotton textiles and jute products in large quantities. With the industrialization of the economy, composition of exports has under gone a change, Thereby the proportion of raw materials in our exports has declined while that of manufactured goods has increased. we are now exporting large quantities of items such as machinery and transport equipment, chemicals allied products, marine products, handicrafts, fish however export of items such as cotton fabric tea Jute

manufactures, spices etc also continues. Our major exports now include manufacturing goods such as Engineering goods, chemicals and related products, Textiles Electronic Goods, Gems & Jewelry, etc. which constitutes over 80 percent of our export basket

Review of Literature:

Mane Vinod H. (2011) has studied the India's direction and composition of foreign trade in the last sixty years. India accepted globalization and liberalization in the year 1991. He shown that India's major exports include manufacturing and engineering goods. Economic development required setting up of new industries, modernization of agriculture and industry. For this, capital goods like machinery, transport equipment's, and raw materials, chemicals and fertilizers, petroleum products etc. are imported. Due to increasing home production of food grains there has been a rapid decline in their imports and now we are self-sufficient in food grains. Our major imports now comprise of capital goods, metals and minerals, chemicals and fertilizers, petroleum, oil and lubricants (POL) etc., which are required to meet the developmental needs of our economy. Today the manufactured goods and services dominate the export basket. The composition of exports shows a perceptible shift in this decade i.e. 2000s from light manufactures to heavy manufactures and petroleum crude and products. **Sathe Dhanmanjiri (1990)** in her thesis has given an analysis of the linkages of foreign trade for the Indian economy (1951 to 1979) to evaluate the performance of exports and imports on the basis of linkages and found that performance of export from period 1951-52, the share of exports in total output has been near about stagnant and the share of exports in the total output was 5.6% in 1951-52, which declined to around 3% in 1968-69. Since then, it has picked up and it became 4.5% in 1978-79. Thus, the changes in exports have not been

in a favorable direction and performances of imports shows that, the imports as a share of total output were 7.4% in 1951-52, and rose in 1978-79 to 5.7%. There has been a remarkable fall in the imports of agricultural goods on the one hand there has been a rise in the importance of manufactured goods. **Bagher Hesamiazizi (2006)** in there thesis he has made an attempt to examine the role of foreign trade in economic growth and development of Indian and Iranian economies. The study conducted for a period of 1960 to 2004 and the data analysis is done using both traditional methodologies, such as common size statements, trend analysis and ratio analysis, correlation regression etc. Based on these results, the study reveals that in pre liberalization period increasing of imports is more than increasing of exports, and increasing of imports led to problems in economic growth. It shows that imports in relation to exports are performing better and post liberalization period export earnings are growing less than imports expenditures i.e. export in relation to import is performing bad so economic growth is less. **Subramanian Srividya (2009)** in there thesis has studied the evaluation of trade policy reforms since 1991 (with emphasis on export promotion instruments). This thesis concluded that the trade policy reforms over nearly two decades enabled perceptible changes in the pattern of trade with manufactured exports attaining dominant share in the export basket viz. engineering goods, petroleum and chemical related products being major exports drivers. The direction of exports shifted to developing countries in the Asian. **Pillania Rajesh K. (2008)** has undertaken exploratory study of India's foreign trade. According to there study, India's foreign trade has progressed a lot over the last sixty years since Independence. The period can be divided into three sub-periods of 1950-1970, 1971-1991 and post 1991. The trade has stagnated and India has lost its market share to other

countries in 1950s and 1960s. The situation improved in 1970s. In terms of composition, now it is dominated by manufactured goods and services. Services exports contribution has grown rapidly in recent past .India's services exports share in global exports is more than that double of Indian manufacturing exports. In terms of direction, it is now more distributed around the world and the share of East Asian countries is on rise in overall trade.

Statement of Problems:

The foregoing review of research literature reveals that definitely some research studies relating to the overall composition of India's foreign and the Performance of exports and Imports have been carried out. All studies focused only on India's external Sector Performance especially export performance during post Reform period. and agricultural exports This paper is provides the picture of exports of indias's manufactured goods in pre and post reforms periods.so it's benefited to understanding present export India manufactured goods in details study for

researchers and equips us about commodity wise exports manufactured goods of India.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To examine the total exports of Manufactured goods share in pre and post reforms period
2. To analyze the total exports of Manufactured goods in pre and post reforms period.

Research Methodology:

The study is based on the secondary data obtained from 1980-81 to 1990-91 and 1991-92 to 2013-14. The data has collected from Annual Reports of Ministry of Finance, Government of India, Economic Survey Reports from 1980-81 to 2013-14 and Handbook of Statistics on Indian Economy 2006-07 & 2013-2014 by Reserve bank of India. For the analysis of composition of Exports and Imports appropriate statistical tools like percentage share, and average values are used. For the analysis of composition of India's foreign trade entire study period is divided into two halves i.e., pre-reform period (1980-81 to 1990-91) and post-reform period (1991-92 to 2013 -14).

Table 1.1: Total Export of Manufactured goods share in pre reform period (Value in Rs)

Year	Total export of Manufactured goods	Total Export of India	Percentage Share
1980-81	4136.27	6710.7	61.64
1981-82	4674.18	7805.88	59.88
1982-83	4671.82	8803.34	53.07
1983-84	5138.73	9770.7	52.59
1984-85	6275.76	11743.7	53.44
1985-86	6449.88	10894.61	59.20
1986-87	8026.67	12451.96	64.46
1987-88	10625.56	15673.66	67.79
1988-89	14641.44	20231.5	72.37
1989-90	19931.67	27658.42	72.06
1990-91	23319.1	32557.63	71.62
Mean	9808.28	14936.55	62.56
SD	6653.59	8464.32	
CV	67.84	56.67	
CAGR	19.48	16.14	

Source: Calculated on the basis of data given in various issues of Economic survey Report, GOI, 1981-1982 to 1986-1987 and Handbook of Statistics on the Indian Economy, RBI, 2000-2001 to 2005-06.

Table 1. 1 represents the data of total export of manufactured goods share in total exports of India in pre reform period. It is seen that proportion of manufactured goods in pre reforms period is 62.56 percent means more than 50 percent manufactured goods

contributed in total export due to modernization. The compound growth rate of export of manufactured goods 19.48 percent annually is greater than that of total export due to the economic reforms during this period.

**Table 1.2: Total Export of Manufactured goods share in post reform period
(Values in Rs. Crore)**

Year	Total export of Manufactured goods	Total Export of India	Percentage Share
1991-92	32413.41	44041.81	73.60
1992-93	40659.81	53688.26	75.73
1993-94	52244.58	69751.39	74.90
1994-95	64067.06	82674.11	77.49
1995-96	79433.34	106353.34	74.69
1996-97	87377.38	118817.08	73.54
1997-98	33635.82	130100.64	25.85
1998-99	108506.18	139753.14	77.64
1999-00	128760.68	159561.39	80.70
2000-01	156858.42	203571.01	77.05
2001-02	159146.4	209017.97	76.14
2002-03	194764.52	255137.28	76.34
2003-04	222828.84	293366.75	75.96
2004-05	272872.33	375339.53	72.70
2005-06	317953	454799.97	69.91
2006-07	384261	571779	67.20
2007-08	414599	655864	63.21
2008-09	566402	840755	67.37
2009-10	546456	845534	64.63
2010-11	719863	1142922	62.98
2011-12	888599	1465959	60.62
2012-13	999612	1635261	61.13
2013-14	1162383	1894182	61.37
2014-15	1210086	1897026	63.79
Mean	368490.95	568552.32	64.81
SD	371169.00	605222.00	
CV	100.73	106.45	
CAGR	17.32	18.00	

Source: Calculated on the basis of data given in various issues of Handbook of Statistics on the

Indian Economy, RBI, 2000-2001 to 2014-15. Table 2 gives the data of total manufactured goods export share in India's total export in percentage. The total contribution of manufactured goods export in post reform era is 64.81 percent. From the year 1990-91 to 2014-15 the contributions of manufactured goods export has indicated a continuous decreasing i.e.73.60 percent to

63.79 percent but compound annual growth rate was decrease as compare to pre reform era i.e.17.32 percent due to liberal the trade. The total export growth rate has 18.00 percent. Manufactured goods and total export has more variability in the export values because after reforms period due to the changing pattern of production and structure of economy.

Table 1.3: Total Export of Manufactured Goods in Pre-reform period
(Values in Rs. Crore)

Year	II. Manufactured goods							Total of Export of Manufactured Goods
	A. Leather and manufactures	B. Chemicals & related products	C. Engineering goods	D. Textile and textile products	E. Gems & jewelry	F. Handicrafts	G. Other Manu. goods	
1980-81	337.13 (8.15) *[-30.57]	226.97 (5.49) *[13.67]	796.86 (19.27) *[2.84]	1406.8 (34.01) *[11.47]	601.92 (14.55) *[15.99]	164.24 (3.97) *[23.10]	602.35 (14.56) *[9.99]	4136.27 (100) *[5.46]
1981-82	369.35 (7.90) *[9.56]	365.54 (7.82) *[61.05]	930.58 (19.91) *[16.78]	1319.52 (28.23) *[-6.20]	761.07 (16.28) *[26.44]	152.18 (3.26) *[-7.34]	775.94 (16.60) *[28.82]	4674.18 (100) *[13.00]
1982-83	360.05 (7.71) *[-2.52]	337.81 (7.23) *[-7.59]	857.88 (18.36) *[-7.81]	1258.2 (26.93) *[-4.65]	949.99 (20.33) *[24.82]	0 (0.00) *[-100.00]	907.89 (19.43) *[17.01]	4671.82 (100) *[-0.05]
1983-84	428.86 (8.35) *[19.11]	316.63 (6.16) *[-6.27]	807.14 (15.71) *[-5.91]	1447.71 (28.17) *[15.06]	1207.36 (23.50) *[27.09]	0 (0.00) *[-]	931.03 (18.12) *[2.55]	5138.73 (100) *[9.99]
1984-85	627.07 (9.99) *[46.22]	459.8 (7.33) *[45.22]	955.99 (15.23) *[18.44]	1920.16 (30.60) *[32.63]	1153.27 (18.38) *[-4.48]	0 (0.00) *[-]	1159.47 (18.48) *[24.54]	6275.76 (100) *[22.13]
1985-86	646.63 (10.03) *[3.12]	359.46 (5.57) *[-21.82]	954.12 (14.79) *[-0.20]	1926.5 (29.87) *[0.33]	1411.62 (21.89) *[22.40]	0 (0.00) *[-]	1151.55 (17.85) *[-0.68]	6449.88 (100) *[2.77]
1986-87	731.21 (9.11) *[13.08]	452.35 (5.64) *[25.84]	1081.34 (13.47) *[13.33]	2448.41 (30.50) *[27.09]	1994.84 (24.85) *[41.32]	0 (0.00) *[-]	1318.52 (16.43) *[14.50]	8026.67 (100) *[24.45]
1987-88	1250.48 (11.77) *[71.02]	1026.35 (9.66) *[126.89]	1494.11 (14.06) *[38.17]	3907.6 (36.78) *[59.60]	2612.73 (24.59) *[30.97]	226.04 (2.13) *[-]	108.25 (1.02) *[-91.79]	10625.56 (100) *[32.38]
1988-89	1522.03 (10.40) *[21.71]	1579.19 (10.79) *[53.86]	2318.89 (15.84) *[55.20]	4399.14 (30.05) *[12.58]	4391.95 (30.00) *[68.10]	298.19 (2.04) *[31.92]	132.05 (0.90) *[21.99]	14641.44 (100) *[37.79]
1989-90	1950.44 (9.79) *[28.15]	2586.99 (12.98) *[63.82]	3325.99 (16.69) *[43.43]	6237.55 (31.29) *[41.79]	5295.53 (26.57) *[20.57]	371.11 (1.86) *[24.45]	164.07 (0.82) *[24.25]	19931.67 (100) *[36.13]
1990-91	2600.25 (11.15) *[33.32]	3100.45 (13.30) *[19.85]	4037.78 (17.32) *[21.40]	7791.82 (33.41) *[24.92]	5246.71 (22.50) *[-0.92]	401.7 (1.72) *[8.24]	140.39 (0.60) *[-14.43]	23319.1 (100) *[17.00]
Mean	983.95 (9.49)	982.87 (8.36)	1596.43 (16.42)	3096.67 (30.89)	2329.73 (22.13)	146.68 (1.36)	671.96 (11.35)	9808.28 (100)
SD	755.35	1008.51	1132.39	2225.99	1805.16	158.92	466.26	6653.59
CV	76.77	102.61	70.93	71.88	77.48	108.35	69.39	67.84
CAGR	23.81	28.83	17.29	20.77	25.83	-	-19.20	19.48

Source: Calculated on the basis of data given in various issues of Economic survey Report, GOI, 1981-1982 to 1986-1987 and Handbook of Statistics on the Indian Economy, RBI, 2000-2001 to 2005-06.

Note: 1. Figure given in Bracket () only indicates percentage share of commodity. 2. * and bracket *[-] Values are related to Annual Growth Rate of commodity.

Table 1.3 represents the composition of Total export of manufactured goods in pre-reform period. It shows the textile & textile product (31) percent and gems and jewelry (22) percent have major contributor as compare to other manufactured goods.. The growth of export of leather and manufacturer is inconsistent (76.77) percent with compound growth rate is 23.81 percent. Chemical & related products has shared 8.36 per cent share of the total manufactured goods. The growth of export of chemical & related products is inconsistent as compound growth rate is 28.83 per cent and coefficient of variation is 102.61 percent. India exported chemical & related products of an average amount Rs.982.87corer in pre-reform period. The commodity engineering goods shared 16.42 per cent share of the manufactured

Conclusion:

Total Export of manufactured goods is growing with compound growth rate of 17.32 percent is less as compare to the pre reforms period was 19.48 percent due to the increasing the export of engineering goods, Gems and jewelry in pre reforms period. The average export of manufactured goods is seen Rs 368490.95 corer in post reforms period with very inconsistence growth while in pre reforms the mean was Rs.9808.28 corer with coefficient of variation 67.84 percent. In pre reforms period Chemicals & related products and Handicrafts very inconsistence growth but in post reforms engineering goods and other Manu. Goods shows inconsistence growth its repressing in tables. The overall research paper has concluded that the manufactured goods export is important to contributing in the total export of India as well as there is significant growth in the post reform era as compare to the pre reform era. Manufactured goods export had been implementing the place of pride in the export basket of India and helpful to push up the Indian economy.

goods. Compound growth rate in export of engineering goods is 17.29 percent per year. Its observed Export of Handicrafts has the least share in the manufactured goods. From the year 1982-83 to 1986-87 the handicraft fails to contribute the total export as well as its very inconsistence growth (108.35) percent during the pre reforms period due to ups and downs in demand. Mean values of total export of other manufactured goods are Rs. 671.96 corer. They shared 11.35 percent of total manufactured goods. Compound growth rate of export of other manufactured goods is -19.20 percent there is very less growth during pre reform period. The average export of manufactured goods is seen Rs 9808.28 corer.

References:

1. Government of India (1981-87), Economic Survey Report 1981-1987, Government of India.
2. Reserve Bank of India (2000-2015), Handbook of Statistics on the Indian Economy, 2000-2001 to 2014-2015, Reserve Bank of India.
3. Mane Vinod H (2011), The India's direction and composition of foreign trade in the last sixty years. Foreign trade Review .Vol.1, Issue IV, pp.3-9.
4. Pillania Rajesh K (2008) An Exploratory Study of Indian Foreign Trade" Journal of Applied Economic Sciences, Vol. III, No.5, Issue3, pp.281-292.
5. Sathe Dhanmanjiri (1990) An analysis of the linkages of foreign trade for the Indian economy (1951 to 1979)." Ph.D.Thesis,Late D.R.Gadgil Library Gokhale institute of politics and Economics, Pune.
6. Bagher Hesamiazizi (2006) The role of foreign trade in economic growth and development of Indian and Iranian economies" ,Ph.D.Thesis,,Pune University,Pune
7. Subramanian Srividya (2009) "Evaluation of trade policy reforms since 1991 (with emphasis on export promotion instruments)."Ph.D.Thesis,Pune University,Pune.